

INNOVATION OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN THE CONTINUOUS EDUCATION SYSTEM - THE NEED OF THE TIME

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ANNOTATSIYA In this article, the current tasks before the technical science of general secondary schools and the psychological, pedagogical and technical-technological aspects of the educational process, the use of interdisciplinary links in the educational process and general secondary education are discussed. Many organizational, legal and scientific research works are being carried out on reforming the system, improving teaching technologies, forming modern knowledge and skills in students, using new teaching methods for this purpose. Through this, it is aimed to create a system of training a generation of competitive and highpotential personnel. This makes the formation of creativity-related skills in students one of the urgent tasks. Therefore, opinions and considerations about the need for innovative tools were made.

Keywords. preschool education, general secondary education, secondary special vocational education, higher education, technology education.

INTRODUCTION In order to modernize education and training processes in the field of socio-economic development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the tasks specified in the Law "On Education", "National Program of Personnel Training" and all stages of the continuous education system of the Cabinet of Ministers up to school education, general secondary education, out-of-school education, secondary special, vocational education, higher education, post-higher education, retraining

and qualification of personnel Reforms are being carried out on the basis of the decisions on improvement of work in the development. Having a high intellectual potential, rich thinking and a broad world view is one of the noble goals of the youth of our country. This can be clearly understood from the enthusiasm of boys and girls who are able to show their talents and abilities in fields such as science, art, and sports. Of course, such positive results are not achieved by themselves. In our country, all opportunities are provided for the young generation to acquire a modern, thorough education, to develop as a mentally and physically mature person. At the moment, the recognition of our achievements based on the "Uzbek model" of education is also a vital confirmation of this idea. The results of the reforms implemented in the education system in our country today arouse the envy of many people. It's not for nothing. Because modern schools, lyceums and vocational colleges that have grown in the remote villages of Uzbekistan are doing good work to encourage students' desire to learn - all this is due to the fact that great attention is paid to the education and upbringing of the young generation in our country. is evidence.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS First President Islam Abduganievich Karimov said, "Our children must be stronger, more educated, wiser and certainly happier than us!" supporting the vital call of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev in his speech "We will build a free and prosperous, democratic country of Uzbekistan together with our brave and noble people" Let's continue. Not only will we continue, but we will raise this policy to the high level required by today's time as our top priority. . Sh. Mirziyoev said that "we need to bring our large-scale work in this field, in particular, to the logical end of our national programs on education", "... the most important task of the education system, our respected teachers and professors is to educate young

people giving a thorough education to the next generation, raising them to become physically and spiritually mature people" defines raising the work aimed at ensuring that young people occupy a worthy place in life to a new level. Also, in the lecture "Our National Army is a solid guarantee of our peaceful, peaceful and prosperous life", he said that "... continuous work on educating our youth in the spirit of patriotism is of urgent importance for us" and the sense of responsibility for the fate of our homeland. All links of the continuing education system are tasked with the need to take concrete measures for strengthening.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION The world community believes that the reforms being carried out in the republic are an important guarantee of the establishment of a humane democratic legal state, the priority of human rights, peace and harmony, and ensuring that our children grow up to be healthy and well-rounded people. is recognized by The issue of modernization in terms of form and content of work carried out at all stages of the continuous education system, that is, the issue of modernization of the education and training process, does not lose its relevance. For this, we need to perform a number of tasks.

Pre-School Education: In order to develop the science of teaching theory and technologies of visual activity, it is necessary to create alternative textbooks and multimedia applications, didactic materials based on the economy of the region, to improve the scientific and methodological support of the science. Preschool education organization Creation of a necessary program to ensure the integration of compulsory one-year preparation of children for primary education with the subjects taught in primary classes. Differentiate the criteria for evaluating children of primary school age according to the age, individual and psychological abilities of students in the cross-section of classes, and achieve a clear definition of its dynamics. It is desirable to introduce didactic games for children using

information about visual activity.

Primary Education: The program "Ensuring the continuity and integrity of preschool, general secondary, professional and higher education curricula and subjects" is structured in accordance with the school program. The program is aimed at forming the necessary skills for students to study, live and work in an industrialized country. At the same time, the program aims to help students to easily escape from labor migration, underdeveloped social infrastructure, poverty and unemployment in the future. Examples of this are the following topics: "Introduction to carpentry and plumbing tools", "Introduction to cooking and sewing tools", "Building and making moving models from various geometric shapes. Making a model of a rocket", "Making mobile devices. Making things that work using a simple mechanism. Stages of making mobile devices (from empty containers), "Understanding the profession of a designer", "Making items from plastic containers." such topics should be included.

General Secondary Education:

1. The inclusion of Agriculture in the curriculum of technological science from the 5th grade has a great connection with other subjects such as botany, biology, chemistry, physics, fine arts.
2. It is necessary to consider the 2 hours of technology lessons in 8-9 grades of secondary schools. Because 1 hour per week is given for mastering subjects in 8-9 grades, there is not enough time for practical training.
3. Since the complex of educational production (UPK) in the 10-11th grades has been completed in general secondary schools, it is necessary to introduce technology subjects in the 10th-11th grades from 1 hour. Because it is possible to ensure consistency and continuity in the formation of professional skills, as well as to connect students to their professional qualifications. 3. In the 5-6-7-8-9 classes

in the direction of service, the department of the basics of construction and modeling is based on the principle of simple to complex, apron processing in the 5th grade, skirt processing in the 6th grade, nightgown processing in the 7th grade, In the 8th grade, it is necessary to include sections on the processing of national shirts, and in the 9th grade, the sections on the processing of modern shirts should be included. Creating the necessary program to ensure connection with other subjects taught at school. Differentiation of evaluation criteria according to the age, individual and psychological characteristics of the student in the cross-section of classes, to achieve a clear definition of its dynamics. There is little information on the fields of electrical engineering, mechatronics and robotics. However, a student's rational use of various electronic tools to meet his daily needs is a sign that school education is lagging behind technological progress. In the 5th grade, information on physics and chemistry is presented. It is difficult for the reader to analyze and synthesize these data. Proposal: It is appropriate to provide information on "Economics" in relation to life. It is desirable to include information on the fields of mechatronics and robotics, simple control algorithms and programs in 5-6 grades.

Secondary Special Education:

1. There are not enough textbooks on sewing profession of primary professional education. It would be appropriate to take into account the sequence of topics in the program when creating textbooks.
2. Uniform video textbooks and visual posters should be created on the basis of the State educational standards for subjects in the program.
3. For primary professional education, it would be appropriate to draw up a single calendar subject plan based on educational programs.
4. Clause 9 of the curriculum of the science of sewing women's clothes for the

tailoring profession 3.53.10.08 of the primary professional education "Peculiarities of processing new types of fabrics. (Content of the topicImprovement of cutting methods for clothing sewn from new types of fabrics. Processing of cuttings with improved construction, i.e. integrated blades are recommended). The subject is abstract. Regarding higher education: the higher education program does not exactly correspond to the State program, the subjects have remained the same. It is necessary to work from scratch. In order to improve the scientificmethodological support of the science of technology, it is necessary to create alternative textbooks and multimedia applications, didactic materials based on the economy of the region.

1. It is necessary to reconsider the content of the practical trainings held in the educational workshop. In this regard, to improve the material technical base by using modern equipment, equipment, devices and small machines.

2. Development of organic science programs to ensure their professional competence in the training of future technological education teachers.

3. To ensure the teaching of a single specialist for the stages of pre-school education, general secondary education, secondary special vocational education, and higher education, to achieve the creation of a single science of technology.

1. It is necessary to include new concepts (terms) related to the science of technology in the continuous education system with their definition in the programs of all stages.

2. Methodologically considering the topics given in the programs, integrating the topics of preschool (group), general secondary school (class), professional education (group) programs into the section of courses in higher education. 6. If educational production workshops (laboratories) rooms of HEIs are built, technological parks for teaching special subjects, conducting scientific research

and laboratory experiments, creating facilities with educational equipment meeting international standards (tools and devices, modern machines) would be appropriate.

7. The subject program "Technology of the organization of agricultural work" given as an elective subject developed at the Higher Education Institution is not included in the concept of ensuring the integrity of technological education.

8. It is necessary to reconsider the content of the practical trainings held in the educational workshop. In this regard, access to modern furniture, equipment, tools and devices, educational materials, laboratory equipment, computers, interactive whiteboards, etc.

SUMMARY In conclusion, "technology" education in general secondary education has a positive effect on the development of creativity skills in students along with hard work. Therefore, it is important to increase students' knowledge about the process of creating techniques and technologies and their use in order to ensure integrity.

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